

**CONSULTATION
REPORT
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Valuing non-financial performance: A European framework for company and investor dialogue

Lloyds TSB

Primary objective

Market value

Financial drivers

Increased sales

Reduced costs

Increased cashflow

Brand value

Risk management

Core non-financial drivers

Human capital

Customer relations

Partnerships

Environment

Innovation

Corporate governance

Key metrics

- Employee engagement

- Customer satisfaction

- Public perception
- Supply chain management

- Carbon emissions
- Waste management
- Lifecycle assessment

- Product/service development

- Ethical integrity
- Board composition

ESG factors

- Absence rate
- Staff turnover
- Health & safety
- Fair restructuring
- Training
- Performance management
- Equality & diversity
- Reputation
- Commitment to customer
- Talent recruitment & retention

- Customer loyalty
- Retention
- Reputation
- Trust
- Price, product, service quality

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- Equality & diversity
- Training & development
- Audit processes
- Reporting & transparency
- Reputation
- Shareholder interests
- Anticorruption policy/practice
- Competitiveness

A framework for dialogue

‘The priority areas of the Alliance will be addressed by “open coalitions of cooperation” bringing together interested companies ready to tackle these issues in the form of “laboratory meetings” in order to explore and to develop joint operational projects, in partnership with relevant experts and stakeholders and with the backing of the European Commission.’

(European Commission CSR White Paper: 22 March 2006)

Transparency and communication is one of the priority areas of the European Alliance for CSR. This laboratory, focused on developing a framework for improved company and investor dialogue on non-financial performance, is contributing to that priority area.

Our work has been taking place against a backdrop of significant turmoil in financial markets, a dynamic environment in which some of our earliest assumptions have been challenged. Two years ago, it was widely accepted that more than 50% of global markets’ value was determined by factors other than 5-year financial performance. Indeed, 2004 research by Accenture indicated that the book value of S&P 500 companies had fallen from 80% to 25% of market value between 1980 and 2002.

Arguably these trends were driving the increasing focus on non-financial performance by mainstream investors and analysts. Exploration of the relationship between non-financial performance and environmental, social and governance (ESG) factors is no longer confined to the socially responsible investment universe. Initiatives such as the UN Principles for Responsible Investment and Enhanced Analytics Initiative could be seen, in part at least, as responses to the need for investor valuation models that better account for non-financial performance.

Now we are in a situation where, possibly, the short-term drivers account for most if not all of current market values. However, we contend that current market dislocation is masking and not reversing the long-term trends. Indeed, that dislocation and its continuing repercussions may reinforce the need to better manage, measure and communicate non-financial performance going forward. Furthermore, we also contend that ESG factors will be increasingly important determinants of non-financial performance as the influence of externalities such as climate change, public and regulatory expectations of business, and the so-called ‘war for talent’ grow.

This consultation report is part of the extensive stakeholder dialogue we are engaged in as one element of testing those contentions which underpin our central proposition. It outlines our current thinking and development of a framework, principles and recommendations for improved dialogue between companies and investors. The laboratory intends finalising its proposals in the first half of 2009.

Central proposition

1. Companies (CEOs) believe their companies would be more highly rated if investors understood more about the non-financial performance of the company;
2. Investors believe they would be better able to assess the future performance of companies if the companies were willing to share more information on key drivers, particularly non-financial drivers;
3. There is a strong correlation between the key non-financial drivers and CSR represented by environmental, social and governance (ESG) factors.

The business case for CSR rests on the assumption that responsible business is better business and those companies that manage their stakeholder relationships well will outperform those companies that don’t (outperform in the sense of delivering better business results and returns to investors).

However, there is a perceived disregard for the CSR agenda in the mainstream investment community. Without demonstrable impact on shareholder value, the willingness of investors to expend time, energy and expense on building ESG factors into valuation models is limited. These valuation models tend to focus on non-financial performance issues, reflecting stakeholder relationships that are viewed by investors as more obviously material to business performance.

So this laboratory is focused on:

- better communication of core non-financial performance as a necessary precursor to a broader and more informed dialogue on the contribution of ESG factors to business performance;

- better understanding the dialogue that currently takes place between business and investors on non-financial performance;
- identifying the key issues that interest investors and how business could better communicate its performance on these issues;
- understanding why businesses see non-financial issues as critical to delivering their business strategy and a fundamental part of the internal performance story but do not include those messages as obviously in external dialogue with investors;
- exploring how ESG performance could be used by individual companies to better articulate their non-financial performance to investors and enrich the story on non-financial contributors to key business strategic priorities.

The laboratory is seeking to develop a framework for dialogue between business and investors that is based on material issues of interest to both. It aims to promote:

- the idea of a common set of core non-financial performance drivers that are relevant across businesses, sectors and markets;
- an acceptance that these core drivers are influenced, at least in part, by the performance and perception of the business by a wide range of stakeholders, reflected in ESG factors, in a way that is more sector or business specific.

By addressing our central proposition - identifying solutions to what we have called the information asymmetry – we believe our framework could help improve companies’ investment performance and increase the importance, the saliency, of non-financial and ESG factors for investors. That is why, despite current circumstances, we are focused on communication and transparency from the perspective of increasing business value.

If both investors and business believe that more and better information will lead to increased business value, that, in itself, is a sufficiently compelling case for improved communication and transparency between business and investors. Furthermore, if that more and better information relates to increasing alignment of stakeholder interests with business strategy, then the business case for CSR starts to become axiomatic.

Research

The Valuing Business research programme

The laboratory is supported by a parallel research programme funded by the European Academy for Business in Society through its corporate founding partners – IBM, Johnson & Johnson, Microsoft, Shell, and Unilever.

The Valuing Business research programme is an initiative to review both current practice in Europe on valuing the strategies and actions businesses adopt in maximising the opportunities presented by Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) factors and to suggest ways of encouraging more companies and more investors to incorporate ESG performance into how businesses are valued. A key concern of this research project is to identify how widely the link between ESG issues and long-term business performance is understood. The main objective is to share ideas and research in a collaborative, open-sourcing approach. It is an attempt to:

- map what is happening;
- create conversations about what more is needed;
- suggest a framework for proposed metrics and strategies for companies and the investment community;
- consider how communication of key areas of their strategies towards ESG factors can be improved, particularly through highlighting the link with financial performance.

Research methods employed include: interviews, action research, documentary analysis and focus group discussions. The Valuing Business research programme is co-ordinated by the Doughty Centre for Corporate Responsibility at the Cranfield School of Management. It involves academics from other leading European business schools including SDA Bocconi School of Management (Milan) and Vlerick Leuven Gent Management School in Belgium; as well as CSR and investment community experts.

What interests investors?

Who are investors? The laboratory has focused on the mainstream investment community of fund managers and analysts who make investment decisions for their own or clients' funds.

While the socially responsible investment (SRI) sector is important, it is still relatively small in terms of market size and influence. Moreover, our central proposition is less relevant as, by its nature, the SRI community is more focused on non-financial and ESG performance.

There is a widespread perception that investors are driven by short term goals, maximising investment performance and shareholder returns. As a result, investors' interest in non-financial performance is limited.

However, in normal times, between 50 and 75% of stock market values are determined by factors other than 5-year future earnings. That is to say the discounted value of forecast 5 year future earnings for a given company will generally account for less than 50% of that company's current market capitalisation.

This indicates that market values are more likely to be determined by investors' perception of businesses likely long-term financial performance – a fact underlined in the current stock market turmoil where pessimism over even short-term earnings has resulted in significant falls in value across markets, accentuated for specific markets and sectors where the pessimism is greatest.

Future financial performance is, in large part, dictated by the way a business is managed now. That is why studies amongst investors often show that investors claim they are as interested in quality of management as current financial performance.

Trends within the investment community

The research programme is undertaking primary research with mainstream investors in a number of major European financial centres. This work continues but preliminary findings indicate limited but increasing interest in non-financial issues.

The increasing trend of institutional investors employing ESG broker teams is facilitating communication between ESG and financial analysts but they generally remain distinct groups with ESG capacity much lower than 'traditional' financial analysis. The use of ESG information in this 'sensibilisation' phase is generally to filter relevant 'material' information – there is an emphasis on risk issues with few signs of cashflow impacts of ESG information impacting on investment thinking. ESG information appears contained to 'decision support' processes; creating a better understanding of companies, development of medium or long-term perspectives, early warning of potential risks and help in identifying future critical challenges. Some key ESG issues are increasingly common concerns across sectors – corporate governance, human capital and environment. There is a tendency to focus on topical themes such as carbon emissions, energy use and age discrimination. However, there are sector specific issues such as labour market impacts on IT, carbon emissions and automotive and climate change and geopolitical risks for insurance. However, there are few standard issues - investors look at only 10-20% of identified ESG factors and only where perceived as material are key themes factored into value, risk and volatility matrices.

What interests investors?

What are the blockages to improved communication of non-financial performance?

From the earliest stages of the laboratory, we identified some key blockages to more effective communication of non-financial performance between companies and investors:

Companies:

- Perceived lack of adequate senior executive expertise in non-financial performance issues and reticence to include in investor presentations unless material to current business strategy.
- Concerns over the robustness of non-financial performance management information and internal methodologies for delivering it.
- Lack of senior executive confidence in the company's ability to manage non-financial performance to the extent of being able to maintain current and forecast future performance.
- Scepticism at investors' interest in non-financial performance.
- Concerns about impact on personal credibility of senior executives promoting messages that are not perceived by investors as core to the financial performance of the business.

Investors:

- Inadequate evidence of causal link between non-financial and financial performance.
- Lack of robust inter-company or sectoral frameworks for comparison of non-financial performance.
- The relative importance of non-financial performance differs between risk and regulatory environments.
- Investor expertise limited to assessment of non-financial performance related directly to the business strategy or leadership competence.
- Lack of willingness to publicise basis of evaluating non-financial performance to protect proprietary analytical tools and approaches as a source of market differentiation, creating lack of transparency in investor methodologies.

These identified key blockages are supported by the preliminary findings of one of the Valuing Business research programme workstreams on the challenges of integrating environmental, social and governance (ESG) factors in making investment decisions. The

research is based on a meta-analysis of over 80 practitioners' reports on ESG risks published since 2000. The reports were qualitatively analysed using Nvivo software to ascertain what practitioners and investors considered were the main obstacles to including ESG issues in investment decisions. Preliminary results suggest 12 factors, often mentioned in practitioners' reports, as the main challenges to making ESG risks integral to investment decisions. Quality of data, trust and difficulties in ascertaining the materiality of ESG risks were top on this list of challenges. Whilst the study is still in progress, it is expected that these preliminary findings will contribute to the ongoing efforts to recognise and incorporate ESG risks in investment decisions. For further details, see: Amaeshi, K. and Grayson, D. (2008). "Count me out: The challenges of environmental, social and governance risks in making investment decisions", a paper presented at the European Academy of Business in Society (EABIS) and the laboratory's workshop at Cranfield in September 2008.

The EFFAS partnership and focus groups

In order to test its proposition, the laboratory has organised five focus groups to collect companies, investors and key stakeholders feedback on the laboratory's broad objectives and, specifically, on the communication framework.

The European Federation of Financial Analysts (EFFAS), through its Commission on ESG issues, played a key role in arranging the meetings, providing the facilities, convening the right people, and providing useful advice. Two focus groups have already taken place in Rome and Frankfurt. Three further focus groups are scheduled:

Paris	11 December 2008
Stockholm	15 January 2009
Amsterdam	date in January 2009 to be confirmed

A summary of the feed back provided by 55 participants in the Rome and Frankfurt focus groups. The numbers reported represent the number of participants scoring responses on a scale of 5 (strongly positive) to 1 (not at all).

Do you think that the information you received during the meeting was enough to get a general understanding of the project, including its objectives and deliverables ?

Do you think that the project can deliver something valuable for the business community and stakeholders ?

Do you think that the project can really contribute in: Improving the communication between companies, investors and other stakeholders?

Developing a model that can be applied in practice?

Enhancing the state of the art of research on these issues?

Which of the following core drivers do you believe to be more relevant in your business activities?

Human capital	17
Customer relations	15
Partnerships	7
Environment	15
Innovation	14
Corporate governance	11

Primary objective

Market value

As a communication focused laboratory, the essence of our approach must inevitably address the primary objectives of the key audiences for that communication. In the interplay between investors and companies, this has to be market value as the most obvious reflection of total shareholder returns.

That said, we have also explored the constituent elements of market value and the relationship to concepts of brand value and accounting value. The diagram below serves to illustrate this.

Here, brand value is the long-term, beyond 5-year earnings, contribution to market value for most companies. While longer-term earnings will account for a significant proportion, this earnings potential is subject to less controllable influences. It is more about investors' perception of the company's ability to manage the factors they will view as material to earnings maintenance and, where brand value is greatest, earnings growth. That is non-financial factors such as human capital, customer relations, partnerships, corporate governance and so on.

Accounting value is a reflection of the asset value of companies. This comprises both tangible and intangible assets. Accounting convention recognises the importance of many classes of intangible assets and these are included in company balance sheets which, in turn, influence

investors' valuations. However, some classes of intangible are not recognised and their influence on investor perception will be more closely related to the degree to which companies can persuade investors as to their materiality. It is in this second class of intangibles that non-financial, CSR or ESG factors are likely to be represented.

The conclusion is: by better informing and demonstrating to investors the company's performance in managing non-financial issues, the more likely investors are to factor them into increased market value, creating what we have defined as extra-financial performance. That is the higher rating by investors that is at the root of our central proposition.

S&P 500, 1980 - 2002

Source: Accenture, July 2004

That is the fundamental limitation of seeking to apply CSR, sustainability or ESG factors directly into financial terms. The materiality of specific factors will differ from business to business, sector to sector, market to market and from time period to time period. More pointedly, many of these factors, by their nature, defy measurement in conventional financial terms or even under the myriad approaches companies adopt to measure non-financial inputs and outputs of internal investment decisions.

This lack of universality and inability to gain consensus on common metrics for a wide range of ESG factors is a problem the laboratory has side-stepped. We will leave that debate to those working on such tools and standards. Our focus has been on identifying a small number of key non-financial performance factors that most directly and demonstrably link to financial performance across sectors and markets and then explore how ESG factors relate to these.

If investors are most concerned with financial performance and non-financial performance that determine future financial performance, then it follows that this has to be the starting point for effective communication between companies and investors. The laboratory has taken the view that non-financial performance has to be mapped against widely accepted key financial drivers. We have adopted those based on Rappaport's model (A. Rappaport: Creating shareholder value (1998)).

This is not new. For example, Bender and Ward seek to demonstrate something similar in their standard textbook on Corporate Financial Strategy. Here they map some examples of sustainability issues onto identified drivers of financial value. As examples, they are difficult to apply in a sufficiently generic way to form the basis of a compelling business case for investors.

Externalising the internalities

Companies already seek to measure and manage key areas of non-financial performance. The contribution of the identified core drivers is often prominent in the company internal strategic story. However, a reticence to articulate this story for investors is a marked feature of the information asymmetry described in our central proposition. One strand of the laboratory's future work is to explore causes and potential solutions. The management and measurement of non-financial performance is often embedded in widely used management models and performance frameworks. The European Foundation for Quality Management's Excellence Model and The Balanced Scorecard are two examples – the former is used by around 30,000 public and private sector organisations across Europe. Lloyds TSB and CSE Associates, a laboratory participant, are developing a paper on this theme with preliminary thinking presented to the recent EABIS Colloquium at Cranfield. It focuses on the interdependence of non-financial performance, the management of ESG factors influencing that performance and consequent business and stakeholder results. The Excellence approach recognises this interdependence of its enabler and results criteria – a concept referred to as 'red threads' - and the challenges of systemising measurable non-financial inputs and outputs in business processes.

Driver of value	Some examples of driving performance through sustainability
Grow sales faster	Innovative products to meet sustainability needs. Attract customers by corporate responsibility stance.
Increase operating profit margin	Better workforce efficiency by treating people better – attract better people, more training, less absenteeism, lower staff turnover. Efficiencies due to energy and waste management.
Reduce cash tax rate	Possibly take advantage of incentives.
Fewer fixed assets	Improved efficiencies.
Less working capital	Reduced waste leading to reduced inventory. Better supply chain practices as companies work in co-ordination.
Increase the period for which the organisation has a competitive advantage	Increased brand equity in the sustainable company. Compliance leads to legitimacy which extends the 'licence to operate'.
Lower cost of capital	Investors perceive lower risk in companies that are compliant with 'best practice' governance regulations.

Core non-financial drivers

Human capital | Customer relations | Partnerships | Environment | Innovation | Corporate governance

The resultant six core non-financial drivers are not surprising. Nor should they be – it would concern us if they were. These core drivers were identified in our earliest deliberations in an intuitive sense and, over the course of consultation and round-table discussions with companies, investors and other stakeholder groups, have created little contention.

In any sense that there were selection criteria, our discussions focused on drivers that:

1. are indicative of wider non-financial performance;
2. could be mapped against finance drivers;
3. have metrics for measurement relevant across businesses, sectors and markets.

However, we were also influenced by the finding of Deloitte's 2007 study *In the Dark II* into the views of CEOs and other senior business leaders. This indicates a widespread consensus within the business community on the main non-financial drivers. The overlap is demonstrated below.

% of directors and top managers believing the following are 'critical' or important drivers of their organisations' success

Deloitte: In the Dark II (2007)

Key metrics

- Employee engagement
- Customer satisfaction
- Public perception
- Carbon emissions
- Product/service development
- Ethical integrity
- Supply chain management
- Waste management
- Board composition
- Lifecycle assessment

A number of key metrics are already established. Others are yet to be finalised and those illustrated in the current version of the framework are current working examples. In the selection criteria for the core non-financial drivers, we determined they should have metrics for measurement relevant across businesses, sectors and markets. This test is met for each of the drivers but the research programme is examining this more extensively. However, we felt it appropriate to include these working examples to stimulate feedback and comment while our work is in progress.

One of the main challenges is that fact that many companies will measure performance against the core drivers in broadly similar ways, reflected in the key metrics suggested. However the exact metrics and bases will not necessarily translate from business to business.

We are not convinced that this is a problem. The emphasis should be on the individual company narrative on: the link between key metrics and delivery of the business strategy (and consequent financial performance); the company's own comparative performance against its variant of the key metrics over time; and the way it is managing improvement activity including the role of ESG factors.

However, if the lack of inter-company or sectoral measures is a significant blockage to investor understanding of the narrative, then this may be a business case for more common approaches to emerge based on sectoral, industry or accounting body initiatives.

ESG factors

- Absence rate
- Staff turnover
- Health & safety
- Fair restructuring
- Training
- Performance management
- Equality & diversity
- Reputation
- Commitment to customer
- Talent recruitment & retention
- Customer loyalty
- Retention
- Reputation
- Trust
- Price, product, service quality
- Opinion former perception
- Media coverage
- Community investment
- Stakeholder dialogue
- Social impact
- Legal/regulatory breaches
- Inclusion
- Energy efficiency
- Deployment of renewables
- Waste reduction
- Recycling
- Environmental impacts
- Environmental breaches
- New products and services
- Value of patents
- Customer perception
- Talent recruitment & retention
- Training
- R&D expenditure
- Nos of non-exec/ independent directors
- Equality & diversity
- Training & development
- Audit processes
- Reporting & transparency
- Reputation
- Shareholder interests
- Anticorruption policy/practice
- Competitiveness

The core non-financial performance metrics are substantially influenced by environmental, social and governance factors. We have identified those factors and mapped them against the ESG framework developed by the European Federation of Financial Analysts (EFFAS). It is not intended that this list is prescriptive or definitive although we are happy if it is considered as such. Some companies have their own or are committed to various standards and frameworks. However, this framework has been developed by EFFAS' ESG Commission. It has been tested with EFFAS members and jointly with the laboratory in focus groups of investors and companies in major European financial markets.

Not all these factors will be relevant across businesses, sectors and markets. Companies need to articulate for themselves how relevant ESG factors influence the key metrics for their business. It is also for individual companies to decide how best this information is presented. We are not recommending that the performance against the relevant factors are published or even measured. The critical issue is how the relevant factors are reflected in the key metrics for the individual company and what action the it is taking on relevant factors to improve performance against the key metrics as part of its business strategy.

The draft principles

The focus of the laboratory's work, so far, has been development of the framework and supporting evidence based on research and stakeholder consultations. However, we have also examined possible application of the framework for companies and investors. In so doing, we have identified a number of principles which we believe will support and guide practical implementation of the framework. We welcome feedback on these draft principles as part of our consultation process.

1. The effective communication of non-financial performance is a prerequisite for enhanced long-term value creation.
2. A critical mass of companies articulating the importance and demonstrating the materiality of non-financial performance will be a major catalyst for increased investor saliency.
3. Identification of the core drivers of non-financial performance and associated key metrics will facilitate more effective communication and investor saliency.
4. Key metrics based on widely established and robust business data collection processes across markets and sectors will enable effective company and investor dialogue.
5. Establishing a relationship between the key metrics and a wider range of ESG factors will enrich companies' strategic commentary on non-financial performance and the materiality of ESG factors for investors.
6. Where core non-financial drivers and key metrics have a direct impact on financial performance, then the ESG factors contributing to those core non-financial drivers also impact on financial performance.
7. Core non-financial drivers and key metrics need to be directly linked to individual business strategies so they are material to investors and incorporated into their valuation models.
8. Where the link between key metrics and ESG factors can be calibrated within an individual business, that business is more likely to want to better measure, manage, and incorporate its performance against those ESG factors in its dialogue with investors.
9. Core non-financial drivers, key metrics and relevant ESG factors need to be integrated into individual business management systems so the credibility of data and any forecast performance can be more easily accepted by investors.
10. The focus on a small number of core non-financial performance drivers, key metrics and relevant ESG factors is more likely to fit with individual companies' existing management models.

The laboratory is exploring recommendations for its final report in mid 2009. These will be based on consultation on the framework and draft principles.

We would welcome views on the implications of the framework and draft principles for the main stakeholders: companies; investors; industry/sector, accounting and management bodies and regulators including the EU Commission. We would also invite suggested recommendations for enabling their widespread adoption.

Recommendations

Companies

Recommendations for adoption?

Investors

Recommendations for adoption?

Industry/sector, accounting and management bodies

Recommendations for adoption?

Regulators

Recommendations for adoption?

Why these core non-financial drivers?

As part of its mission, the laboratory intends to underpin its identified core non-financial performance drivers and key metrics with a significant body of evidence of their contribution to financial drivers. We also intend to make the link to relevant ESG factors through company evidence and case studies. This evidence, also a key output of the research programme, will be published in a report in the first half of 2009. Here, by way of example, we provide case studies for human capital (driver) and employee engagement (metric) and corporate governance (driver) and ethical integrity (metric).

Employee engagement

Employee engagement is a higher form of employee satisfaction; an emotional commitment to the organisation people work for, translated into a willingness to invest discretionary effort in contributing to its success. Most businesses measure employee satisfaction in some form, many already measure employee engagement.

There is an established link between employee engagement and financial performance, generally but not exclusively through the impact of engaged employees on customer perception. These employee-customer-shareholder value chains have been well elaborated by a number of companies.

How employee engagement is measured is not critical for the purposes of this laboratory. There are a number of established metrics in use by companies – the Towers Perrin-ISR model is a widely used one. It is the fact that these metrics are used, and linked to the business strategy and the ESG factors that influence them articulated by businesses that is most critical.

Towers Perrin-ISR have also established the factors influencing employee engagement across a wide variety of sectors. There are variations but the evidence suggests a common set of components. These components are well reflected in the ESG factors of our framework.

Towers Perrin-ISR studies have demonstrated a compelling link between workforce engagement and financial performance

A 12-month study across 50 global companies

A three-year study across 40 global companies

Top 10 engagement drivers

- 1 Senior management interest in employee well-being
- 2 Opportunities to improve skills and capabilities
- 3 Organization's reputation for social responsibility
- 4 Input into decision-making
- 5 Organization quickly resolves customer concerns
- 6 Setting high personal standards
- 7 Career advancement opportunities
- 8 Challenging work assignments that broaden skills
- 9 Good relationship with supervisor
- 10 Organization encourages innovative thinking

Source: Towers Perrin-ISR 2007 workforce study - global

Lloyds TSB uses the Towers Perrin-ISR metric. Its analysis has identified six primary determinants of employee engagement in Lloyds TSB. These determinants are well represented in the Framework's ESG factors. They are now measured in a tracked quarterly employee engagement survey; the employee engagement index; completed by over 70% of all employees. Increasing employee engagement in Lloyds TSB is a key part of its business strategy, a corporate responsibility priority and the index score is one of the primary performance measures in the organisation's Balanced Scorecard.

Corporate governance: Does business ethics pay?

The UK's Institute of Business Ethics seminal 2003 research into the correlation between companies' use of codes of ethics and business performance against a range of financial measures was followed up in 2007 with this rigorous statistical analysis of company performance and more infrastructural ethical criteria.

The research tested whether:

1. companies with Corporate Applied Ethics perform better financially than those only with Corporate Revealed Ethics and
2. business ethics has a stronger impact on accounting-based measures or market-based indicators.

Four financial performance measures (return on capital employed, return on assets, total shareholder return and market value added) were analysed. The financial performance measures were adjusted for size, risk and price-to-book value as these are some of the factors that affect a firm's performance.

The long run analysis, in the five years 2001-2005, showed a significantly greater positive relationship between provision of training for business ethics (Corporate Applied Ethics) and financial performance compared to those which only disclosed ethical values and their financial performance.

The study also found that accounting-based measures are more influenced by business ethics training than market based indicators.

The results of this research are consistent with the expectation that companies with a demonstrable ethics programme benefit from the confidence that is instilled in their stakeholders. This facilitates reputation building, enhances relations with bankers and investors, helps firms attract better employees, increases goodwill, leaves the firms better prepared for external changes, turbulence and crisis and generally helps the firm run better.

Leaders and facilitators

EABIS
European Academy
of Business in Society

Research

Doughty Centre for Corporate
Responsibility at Cranfield School
of Management
SDA Bocconi School
of Management
Vlerick Leuven Gent
Management School

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Participants

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However, their participation does
not necessarily imply endorsement
of the laboratory's final conclusions.

Business

PricewaterhouseCoopers
Accenture
CSE Associates
Deloitte
State Street
ENI
SNS Reaal
Tomkins
Radley Yeldar
Epson Europe
ENEL
Monte dei Paschi di Siena
Jupiter Asset Management
Fortis
Towers Perrin-ISR
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NGOs and associations

EFFAS - European Federation of
Financial Analysts
AIAF .- Associazione Italiana
Analisti Finanziari
DVFA - Society of Investment
Professionals in Germany
Report Leadership
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Investor Relations Society
Greenpeace
WWF
Legambiente
Confindustria SIT
Fondaca

EU Commission

DG Enterprise & Industry
DG Employment & Social Affairs
DG Trade
DG Internal Market

Feedback

We would welcome your feedback on this consultation
report as a contribution to our work. Please post your
comments on the laboratory's website at
www.investorvalue.org before 28 February 2009.

We would particularly welcome your response to the
following questions:

1. Do you think the information contained in this report is
adequate to gain a general understanding of the
laboratory's work including its objectives and
deliverables? What more would you like to know?
2. What can the laboratory's framework contribute to
improved dialogue between companies and investors?
3. How well can the framework be applied in your
practical experience?
4. Are the principles relevant to the dialogue between
companies and investors?
5. What recommendations are required to enable
widespread adoption of the framework and principles
– by companies, investors, accounting and industry
bodies and regulators?
6. What further research is necessary in this area?
7. Would you welcome the opportunity to participate in
development of the laboratory's work?

For information on all the Laboratories under the
European Alliance for CSR, access the website at
www.csreurope.org/toolbox.